

1 Massive Missing Data Reconstruction in Ocean Buoys
2 with Evolutionary Product Unit Neural Networks

3 A. M. Durán-Rosal^{a,b}, C. Hervás^a, A.J. Tallón-Ballesteros^c, A.C.
4 Martínez-Estudillo^d, S. Salcedo-Sanz^e

5 ^a*Department of Computer Science and Numerical Analysis, Universidad de Córdoba,*
6 *Rabanales Campus, 14071 Córdoba, Spain.*

7 ^b*Corresponding author: Antonio M. Durán-Rosal. Department of Computer Science and*
8 *Numerical Analysis, Universidad de Córdoba. 14071 Córdoba, Spain. Ph: +34*
9 *957218349, email: i92duroa@uco.es*

10 ^c*Department of Languages and Computer Systems, Universidad de Sevilla, 41012 Seville,*
11 *Spain.*

12 ^d*Department of Management and Quantitative Methods, Universidad Loyola Andalucía,*
13 *41014 Seville, Spain.*

14 ^e*Department of Signal Processing and Communications, Universidad de Alcalá, 28805*
15 *Alcalá de Henares, Madrid, Spain.*

16 **Abstract**

In this paper we tackle the problem of massive missing data reconstruction in ocean buoys, with a Evolutionary Product Unit Neural Network (EPUNN). When considering a large number of buoys to reconstruct missing data, it is sometimes difficult to find a common period of completeness (without missing data on it) in the data to form a proper training and test set. In this paper we solve this issue by using partial reconstruction, which are then used as inputs of the EPUNN, with linear models. Missing data reconstruction in several phases or steps is then proposed. In this work we also show the potential of EPUNN to obtain simple, interpretable models in spite of the non-linear characteristic of the network, much simpler than the commonly used sigmoid-based neural systems. In the experimental section of the paper we show the performance of the proposed approach in a real case of massive missing data reconstruction in 6 wave-rider buoys at the Gulf of Alaska.

17 *Keywords:* Significant wave height; Missing values reconstruction; Product
18 Unit Neural Networks; Evolutionary Algorithm.

19 1. Introduction

20 Oceanographic buoys are measuring instruments used, among other pur-
21 poses, to characterize wind-generated wave properties. The availability and
22 accuracy of buoys data is crucial in very different problems and applications
23 such as the design and maintenance of marine/coastal structures, wave height
24 forecasting for safe ship navigation, or the design and operation of wave en-
25 ergy converters, etc. (López et al., 2013). There are different agencies such
26 as the National Data Buoy Centre (NDBC) of the USA, that maintain a
27 large network of OBs to collect wave data on a regular basis (Londhe, 2008).
28 A number of unexpected events can make buoys break down (such as storms
29 (Rao and Mandal, 2005), navigation accidents, maintenance periods, etc),
30 causing data gaps, and therefore discontinuities in the buoys data time se-
31 ries, lasting from the causing event until the buoy is repaired/maintained.
32 Some data analysis methods may allow gappy data (Liu and Wisberg, 2005),
33 while most statistical methods require data to be gaps free (Thomson and
34 Emery, 2014). Due to this point, the reconstruction of missing wave values
35 has become a key topic in oceanic research.

36 Very different techniques for recovering of lost/missing OB data have been
37 proposed in the last three decades, with prevalence of techniques focussed on
38 reconstruction of wave height data. The first approaches were quite naive,
39 such as random sampling of data points suggested in Thompson (1971), or
40 Monte Carlo methods applied to fill up gaps at random in a known time
41 series of monthly mean sea level in Sturges (1983). In more recent works
42 such as Soares and Cunha (2000); Agrawal and Deo (2002), auto-regressive,
43 auto-regressive moving average (ARMA) or auto-regressive integrated mov-
44 ing average (ARIMA) have been successfully applied to reconstruction of
45 wave heights time series. Other constructive techniques such as cubic splines
46 or fractal methods have been recently tested in wave height reconstruction
47 problems (Liu et al., 2014).

48 In recent years, the number of works applying data Machine Learning
49 (ML) techniques have been massive. Among ML techniques, neural net-
50 works (NNs) (Haykin, 1998) may have been the most used prediction meth-
51 ods. In Bhattacharya et al. (2003), NNs have been used to compute missing
52 wave data in time series, measured at Europlatform station, in the North
53 Sea. NNs have been found to be specially reliable to reach accurate estima-
54 tions of missing wave data (Balas et al., 2004). In that work, feedforward
55 Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs) and recurrent neural networks were trained

56 by the steepest descent with momentum algorithm and the conjugate gra-
57 dient algorithm, and their estimations were compared to those computed
58 by using conventional stochastic models. The recurrent neural network ap-
59 proach trained by the conjugate gradient algorithm was found to predict
60 wave height, period, and direction more accurately than the NN. In Gunay-
61 din (2008), the prediction of significant wave heights using neural networks,
62 trained with the classical back-propagation algorithm in three stations in
63 the Atlantic area has been carried out. In Londhe and Panchang (2007) the
64 problem of reconstructing lost information from buoys by applying neural
65 networks trained with Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm in the north-eastern
66 part of United States was tackled. In Malekmohamadi et al. (2008) a NN
67 coupled to a numerical prediction model was used to obtain wave height
68 prediction/reconstruction values. Results in buoys located at lake Superior
69 and in the Pacific Ocean were used to validate the model. In Zamani et al.
70 (2008) a NN with k-nearest neighbor algorithm has been applied to a prob-
71 lem of wave estimation using significant heights in previous hours. Results
72 in two buoys located at Caspian sea have shown a good agreement of the
73 prediction with real data. In Arena and Puca (2004) the use a Multivariate
74 Neural Network for the reconstruction of significant wave height time series
75 was proposed, and in Setiawan et al. (2008) alternative methodologies for
76 training neural networks are introduced, including some concepts from the
77 Rough Set theory.

78 NNs and Genetic Programming (GP) (Koza, 1992) were successfully ap-
79 plied in Londhe (2008) to estimate missing wave heights from neighbouring
80 stations heights measurements. Six buoys from Gulf of Mexico were used,
81 and results obtained showed a good reconstruction of weight heights using
82 these techniques. GP and NNs have also been applied to wave forecast from
83 wind data in Nitsure et al. (2012), obtaining good results in data from the
84 east coast of the USA and India. Also using the data from adjacent buoys,
85 significant wave height values at a buoy location have been estimated by
86 means of a Neuro-Fuzzy approach (Özger, 2009) based on Sugeno-type fuzzy
87 inference. In that paper, the antecedent and consequent part parameters of
88 the fuzzy IF-THEN rules have been inferred after training the fuzzy infer-
89 ence system by the Adaptive Neuro Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) method
90 (Jang, 1993). The experimental work was also carried out by using data mea-
91 sured by buoys located at the Gulf of Mexico. NN and ANFIS methods were
92 tested in a problem of wave parameters estimation in Mahjoobi et al. (2008),
93 over lake Ontario data obtained from a deep-water buoy. In Kalra and Deo

94 (2007), particular GP models based on spatial correlation with neighboring
95 values have been applied to wave height estimation. The results suggest that
96 GP achieves slightly better results than the NNs explored by the authors in
97 previous works. In a similar scientific standpoint, Ustoorikar and Deo (2008)
98 leads to the conclusion that gaps of missing values are slightly better com-
99 puted by the GP algorithm than those estimated by the NN designed for
100 comparative purposes, in particular if the gaps of missing values are small.
101 Radial basis functions (RBF) have also been applied to similar problems like
102 in Camus et al. (2011), where this class of neural network was applied to
103 a problem of down-scaling waves data to shallow waters. There have been
104 alternative approaches that hybridize physical/numerical methods with sta-
105 tistical or ML approaches, such as Casas-Prat et al. (2014), where different
106 predictive variables from numerical models are hybridized with linear regres-
107 sion for wave height estimation, or Fernández et al. (In Press, 2015), that used
108 predictive variables from numerical methods hybridized with different ordi-
109 nal classifiers for discrete wave height estimation in the gulf of Alaska. Some
110 kernel methods have also been applied to wave height prediction problems
111 such as Mahjoobi and Mosabbebeh (2009), where support vector regression al-
112 gorithms were using different kernels where applied to wave height estimation
113 in Lake Michigan.

114 Other approaches for wave height missing data imputation are based on
115 evolutionary algorithms. One of this works is Nelwamondo et al. (2007), that
116 compares expectation maximisation (EM) techniques and auto-associative
117 neural networks and genetic algorithms in the scope of industrial data. Ge-
118 netic Algorithms and Neural Networks were evaluated to approximate miss-
119 ing data with a variable number of missing values within a register in Abdella
120 and Marwala (2005). The approach in Medina and Serrano-Hidalgo (2004) is
121 based on the use of pruned neural network models optimized by evolutionary
122 strategies and the utility function concept. The method is applied to recon-
123 struct the time series of the significant wave height of a wave buoy at Bilbao
124 on the northern coast of Spain. Evolutionary multi-layer perceptron models
125 trained via genetic algorithms have been recently proposed in Altunkaynak
126 (2013).

127 Finally, there have been studies of missing values of spatio-temporal wave
128 time series. One of the first works to interconnect data from multiple stations
129 was Tsai et al. (2002). In Ho and Yim (2005) the possible interrelationships
130 between two stations, which are 20 km away from each other, by means of
131 transfer function, was analyzed and more recently, a neuro-fuzzy strategy was

132 proposed in Özger (2009) to recover the data from a buoy with the recorded
133 information in their neighbour buoys.

134 In all these previous works based on measurements from neighbor buoys,
135 the method is the following: first, complete time periods in all the buoys in-
136 volved in the reconstruction (the inputs and the objective one) are obtained.
137 Then, the algorithms are trained using part of these data, and the perfor-
138 mance of the reconstruction is evaluated in the remainder of the data (test
139 set). Once the algorithms are trained, missing values in the objective buoy
140 can be reconstructed by using the corresponding values in the input buoys.
141 The main issue with this method is observed in cases with massive missing
142 data in some buoys, or cases with a large number of buoys, in which it is very
143 difficult to obtain large periods of common non-missing values. In the case
144 of using ML techniques to missing data reconstruction, there is an additional
145 drawback: the lack of interpretability inherent to these techniques. These
146 methods are usually highly non-linear, with a strong ability in obtaining in-
147 formation from data, but very difficult to interpret in terms of predictive
148 (physical) variables.

149 With the previous ideas in mind, the objective of this paper is twofold: on
150 one hand, we propose a method for buoy missing data reconstruction in the
151 case of massive amount of data that do not allow obtaining large complete
152 periods for training the algorithms. In order to do this, we apply well-
153 known linear models (transfer functions (Ho and Yim, 2005) and neighbor
154 correlation (Paulhus and Kohler, 1952)) combined with Product Unit Neural
155 Networks (PUNN), to form a method that allows a complete reconstruction
156 of missing data, using partial reconstruction from linear approaches. On
157 the other hand, PUNN networks have the property that linear models can
158 be obtained from them by taking logarithms in the networks output, so
159 we finally come up with linear interpretable models, but constructed using
160 nonlinear procedures, which partially solves the issue about non-linearity of
161 ML methods. The procedure proposed in this paper have obtained excellent
162 results in terms of missing value reconstruction in a case with a large number
163 of buoys involved in the Gulf of Alaska, with interpretable models that can
164 be discussed in terms of predictive variables.

165 This paper aims to provide a method of automatic reconstruction of time
166 series with massive missing values. Our purpose is to use EPUNN, where
167 the inputs of the networks are the partial reconstruction obtaining by linear
168 methods previously, to improve others basic functions in terms of accuracy
169 and simplicity. Futhermore, combining these approaches (linear and non-

170 linear methods), we apply the proposed method in the reconstruction of the
 171 wave height of 6 wave-rider buoys at the Gulf of Alaska.

172 The rest of the paper is structured as follows: next section presents the
 173 EPUNN method proposed. Linear models serving as input for proposed
 174 PUNN are also described at this section. Section 4 presents the experimen-
 175 tal part of the paper, where the performance of the proposed models are
 176 evaluated. First, a description of the missing values reconstruction Scenario
 177 (Alaska) is described. The results obtained in this problem are shown dis-
 178 cussed in this section. Finally, Section 5 closes the problem with some final
 179 comments and remarks on the research carried out.

180 2. Product Unit neural networks

181 Artificial NNs can be considered similar to basis function models (Denison
 182 et al., 2002). These models assume that the network output g is made up of
 183 a linear combination of basis functions and corresponding coefficients. Hence
 184 g can be written as:

$$g(\mathbf{x}) = \beta_0 \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_j \cdot B_j(\mathbf{x}), \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^k \quad (1)$$

185

$$B_j = \prod_{i=1}^k x_i^{w_{ji}} \quad (2)$$

186 where $\boldsymbol{\beta}=(\beta_1, \dots, \beta_m)^T$ is the set of coefficients corresponding to linear part
 187 of the model, and $\mathbf{W}=(\mathbf{w}_1, \dots, \mathbf{w}_m)$ is the set of coefficients corresponding to
 188 basis functions $\mathbf{B} = (B_1, \dots, B_m)$, therefore the complete set of coefficients
 189 is $\boldsymbol{\Theta}=(\mathbf{w}_1, \dots, \mathbf{w}_m, \boldsymbol{\beta})$. These basis functions are considered, in general, sig-
 190 moidal, but standard neural networks with sigmoidal basis functions require
 191 a large number of units when approximating complex functions, that involve
 192 higher order combinations of its inputs (Leerink et al., 1995). Different alter-
 193 native basis functions have been proposed in the literature. Among others,
 194 we can mention radial basis functions (Lee and Hou, 2002), q-gaussian radial
 195 basis functions (Fernández-Navarro et al., 2011), general regression networks
 196 (Tomandl and Schober, 2001), new models of networks for regression and
 197 classification (Arulampalam and Bouzerdoum, 2003), or networks of product
 198 units, that utilize higher-order combinations of multiplicative neurons, what
 199 greatly reduce the number of processing units required to represent complex

200 functions (Janson and Frenzel, 1993; Durbin and Rumelhart, 1989; Martínez-
201 Estudillo et al., 2006, 2008). Product unit basis functions are among the most
202 interesting basis function models. They are, in general, multiplicative neu-
203 ral networks that contain nodes that multiply their inputs instead of adding
204 them, and thus allow inputs interacting nonlinearly.

205 As we can see in Equation 2 a PUNN is a high-order network, where a
206 node of the hidden layer is now a product of terms; each term consisting
207 of an input raised to a weight, where k is the number of inputs. If the ex-
208 ponents are $\{0, 1\}$ we obtain a higher-order unit, also well-known under the
209 name of *sigma-pi* unit. In contrast to the sigma-pi unit, in the product unit
210 (PU) the exponents are not fixed and may even take real values. Advan-
211 tages of PUNNs are increased information capacity and the ability to form
212 higher-order combinations of the inputs. In Durbin and Rumelhart (1989) it
213 was determined empirically that the information capacity of product units
214 (measured by their capacity for learning random Boolean patterns) is ap-
215 proximately $3k$, compared to $2k$ of a network with additive units for a single
216 threshold logic function. Also it is possible to obtain upper bounds of the
217 Vapnik-Chervonenkis (VC) dimension for product unit neural networks simi-
218 lar to those obtained for sigmoidal neural networks (Schmitt, 2002). PUNNs
219 have the ability to express strong interactions between input variables, pro-
220 viding large variations at the output from small variations at the inputs.
221 Consequently, they have increased storage information capability and po-
222 tential for time series data imputation. However this, PUNNs result in a
223 highly convoluted error function, plenty of local minima, which makes very
224 hard the correct training of these networks. This handicap makes convenient
225 the use of global search algorithms rather than back-propagation or gradient
226 methods, since it is a well-known issue (Ismail and Engelbrecht, 2000) that
227 back-propagation is not efficient in training product units networks.

228 Different global search meta-heuristic algorithms have been tried in PUNN
229 training, such as Genetic Algorithms (Janson and Frenzel, 1993), Particle
230 Swarm Optimization approaches (Ismail and Engelbrecht, 2000). Over the
231 past decade, it has developed genetic programming algorithms, that jointly
232 learn the network topology and the weights of the connections have been
233 proposed to train PUNN for classification (Hervás-Martínez and Martínez-
234 Estudillo, 2007; Martínez-Estudillo et al., 2008) and regression problems
235 (Martínez-Estudillo et al., 2006).

236 The neural network model is an instance of model-free or non-parametric
237 regression. When a training sample $D = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{y}_i); i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is available,

238 where $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_{1i}, \dots, x_{ki})$ is the vector of measurements taking values in $\Omega \subset$
 239 \mathbb{R}^k , and \mathbf{y}_i is the response variable. This data set have been generated from
 240 unknown models. Based on the training sample, we wish to find a regression
 241 function defined in Equation 1 and 2.

242 Note that main problem in this kind of models is to estimate these coeffi-
 243 cient (w_i). In this work we apply an evolutionary algorithm (EA) to estimate
 244 them, following the good results obtained in Hervás-Martínez et al. (2007).
 245 The general structure of the algorithm is the following:

- 246 1. Generate the initial population of individuals, encoding different values
 247 for Θ .
- 248 2. Repeat until the stopping criterion is fulfilled:
 - 249 • Calculate the fitness of every individual in the population (given
 250 by a predefined error measure of the PUNN in the problem at
 251 hand, the root mean squared error, RMSE, int this paper).
 - 252 • Rank the individuals regarding their fitness.
 - 253 • The best individual is copied into the new population.
 - 254 • 10% of the best individuals in the population are replicated and
 255 substitute 10% of worst individuals. This produces a small se-
 256 lective pressure that has shown useful in the convergence of the
 257 algorithm. This value has been obtained by means of a 5-fold
 258 crossvalidation over the training set (Gutiérrez et al., 2009).
 - 259 • Apply parametric mutation to 10% of the best individuals.
 - 260 • Apply structural mutation to the rest of the 90% of individuals.
- 261 3. The best individual at the end of the evolution Θ^* is considered as the
 262 solution to the problem.

263 In this paper, EPUNN are applied to partially reconstructed data from
 264 Linear Models (LM), by using the outputs of these LM as inputs of the
 265 network. Two well-known LM methodologies based on the correlation coeffi-
 266 cients between the time series are applied: Transfer functions (Ho and Yim,
 267 2005) and linear neighbor models (Paulhus and Kohler, 1952).

268 *2.1. Linear model 1: Transfer Functions*

269 This method consists of analyzing the correlations and estimate a lin-
 270 ear function between an incomplete time series of wave height with other

271 *complete* ones (without gaps at the considered reconstruction time periods).
 272 To do so, for each incomplete time series, the correlation with a complete
 273 (without gaps) time series must be higher than an a given threshold α , to
 274 participate in the transfer function. Note that, when a time series is recov-
 275 ered, this time series is considered as complete (without gaps) for the next
 276 incomplete buoy, so it is necessary to increase the threshold in order to re-
 277 duce the error made in the reconstruction. The main steps of this method
 278 are summarized in the following pseudocode:

279 **Transfer functions method:**

280 **Require:** Incomplete and complete time series.

281 **Ensure:** Recovered time series.

- 282 1: Initialize α .
- 283 2: **while** time series are incomplete **do**
- 284 3: Calculate the correlations between an incomplete time series with the
 285 complete time series, using common values over time.
- 286 4: **for** each time series (Y) whose correlations with the complete time
 287 series (X_i, \dots, X_n) is greater than α **do**
- 288 5: Calculate a linear regression:
 289 $Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1t} + \dots + \beta_i X_{it} + \dots + \beta_n X_{nt}, \quad t = 1, \dots, n$
- 290 6: Estimate the missing values with the previous function.
- 291 7: Obtain the error measure (RMSE, r^2 , etc.).
- 292 8: **end for**
- 293 9: Each time series Y is considered as a new complete one.
- 294 10: $\alpha = \alpha + \Delta\alpha$.
- 295 11: **end while**

296 *2.2. Linear model 2: Neighbours method*

297 The second LM method applied in this paper is the neighbor LM, obtained
 298 by means of a modifying expression proposed in Paulhus and Kohler (1952).
 299 This LM allows estimating the missing values in a time series, adding the
 300 information of the correlation coefficients between this series and a complete
 301 one. This method is faster than the previous one because it only needs one
 302 iteration for each time series in each time instant to complete it. The original
 303 expression for this method is the following:

$$\hat{Y}_t = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\bar{Y} \cdot X_{it}}{\bar{X}_i} \quad (3)$$

304 where \hat{Y}_t is the estimated time series Y in the instant t , N is the number of
 305 time series with values in t , \bar{Y} is the average of the values of Y , X_{it} is the
 306 value of the time series X_i in t , and \bar{X}_i is the average value of this time series.

307 After introducing the correlation between time series, the final expression
 308 applied in this paper is the following:

$$\hat{Y}_t = \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i \frac{\bar{Y} \cdot X_{it}}{\bar{X}_i} \quad (4)$$

309 where α_i is defined as follows:

$$\alpha_i = \frac{r_{YX_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^N r_{YX_i}} \quad (5)$$

310 where r_{YX_i} is the correlation coefficient between Y and X_i .

311 3. Methodology and data used

312 In this section we first described the methodology proposed in this pa-
 313 per for missing data reconstruction in buoys, and then we describe the real
 314 case tackled in the experimental section of the paper, consisting of the real
 315 reconstruction of missing data for 6 buoys at the Gulf of Alaska, USA.

316 3.1. Proposed methodology

317 The methodology followed in this paper is the following: first we con-
 318 sider a case with a large number of buoys, in which it is not possible to
 319 obtain large common complete intervals to train the methods. Instead, we
 320 propose to follow a sequential mechanism of reconstruction with LM mod-
 321 els, and a final reconstruction step with EPUNN, considering as inputs the
 322 reconstructed time series values from LM models. For each time series of sig-
 323 nificant wave height we set a 20% of the complete data for testing purposes.
 324 Note that this set is not common to all buoys, but it will be fixed for all the
 325 methods considered, as intuitive. The remainder 80% of available data form
 326 the training set. With this initial data, we apply both LM considered in a
 327 separate way. Thus we obtain 2 different initial reconstruction of the time
 328 series. The EPUNN is then applied based in the reconstructed time series. It
 329 first calculates the correlation between time series, and it considers the two
 330 most correlated ones to reconstruct the objective time series. The EPUNN
 331 is applied over available data or data previously reconstructed with the best
 332 LM previously applied. Figure 1 summarizes the proposed methodology.

333 *3.2. Buoys at the Gulf of Alaska*

334 In this paper we consider 6 buoys located at the Gulf of Alaska: Specif-
335 ically, they are buoys belonging to the National Buoy Center of the USA
336 (<http://www.ndbc.noaa.gov/>, 2015), with registration number 46001, 46061,
337 46076, 46078, 46082 and 46085 (see Figure 2). In the proposed analysis,
338 data from 1st January 2008 to 31st December 2013 (6 hours resolution) are
339 considered for 6-hour time horizon reconstructions (a value of the buoys each
340 6 hours). In a first analysis of the data, we found that the correlations of
341 buoys 46061, 46076 and 46082 (nearby coast) at time $t + 1$ is larger with
342 the rest of buoys (offshore buoys) at time t (instead of at time $t + 1$). This
343 fact made us to consider these 3 buoys at time $t + 1$, whereas the rest of the
344 buoys data are managed at time t . Finally, the time series are divided into
345 80%/20% to training/testing the methodologies. A summary of the buoys'
346 characteristics are given in Table 1. Note that buoy 46001 is complete, and
347 the rest of the buoys considered have an important amount of missing data.

348 **4. Results and discussion**

349 The experiments performed and the results obtained are analyzed in this
350 section. First of all we present the experimental setting considered, and then
351 we show the results obtained in the problem of missing data reconstruction
352 in Gulf of Alaska buoys.

353 *4.1. Experimental setting*

354 For the first LM method (transfer functions), the initial threshold has
355 been set to $\alpha = 0.75$, and it is increased 0.05 in each iteration of the algo-
356 rithm. The threshold has been determined by an experimental design which
357 uses a 5-fold cross-validation over the training set using a grid for alpha val-
358 ues of 0.65, 0.70 and 0.75. The EA to train the neural networks (PUNN
359 and SUNN) has been configured with the following parameters values, ex-
360 perimentally obtained in a previous step: the number of individuals of the
361 population has been set to 1000. The minimum and maximum number of
362 neurons for the initial population, and the maximum number of neurons
363 along evolution are set to 1, 2, and 2 respectively. The maximum number
364 of generations is 100. For the structural mutation, the number of neurons
365 to add/remove was configured between 1 and 2, and the number of links to

366 add/remove between 1 and 4¹. Finally, the parametric mutation is set to
367 add a random value from a Gaussian distribution of mean 0 and variance
368 1. Given the stochastic nature of the proposed EAs, our algorithm was run
369 30 times with different seeds, and we selected the best one in terms of the
370 fitness function and simplicity (minimum number of links).

371 4.2. Results

372 First of all, we show the initial reconstruction results with LM models.
373 In order to work with correlation coefficients, they have been calculated,
374 and shown in Table 2. The models and RMSE obtained using the *transfer*
375 *functions* LM are shown in Table 3. The procedure followed in this case is
376 summarized in Figure 3. In the case of the *neighbor* LM, there are no models
377 to show, but the reconstruction is carried out using Equation (4). The results
378 obtained with this second LM are shown in Table 4.

379 After this first reconstruction step by LMs, we apply the PUNN proposed
380 in this paper, taking into account the best output (less RMSE) of the LMs
381 (best reconstructed time series, which are time series of significant wave
382 height of buoys 46061, 46078, 46082 and 46085 of first linear method, and
383 of buoy 46076 of the second one) as input variables. These results can be
384 seen in Table 5. For comparison purposes, we have also included the results
385 obtained with a neural network using sigmoid units in Table 6. We can
386 observe that, in general, better results are obtained, as expected, with PUNN
387 neural networks (the difference in terms of reconstruction error is not large,
388 but less parameters are used in this case). Good reconstruction results are
389 obtained with the proposed method, in terms of r^2 values, with figures over
390 0.9. In the time series ($H_s(m)$) with the largest number of data missing,
391 the reconstruction has less quality, with a r^2 about 0.75. Note that sigmoid
392 units also obtain good results in the reconstruction, but differences are not
393 significant with the PUNN, and the models obtained with this neural network
394 are much more complicated. Note that in general, the reconstruction error
395 made is larger for offshore buoys. Figure 4 shows the scatter plots obtained by
396 the PUNN in the reconstruction of the 5 buoys with missing values considered

¹Structural mutation modifies the topology of the neural nets, helping the algorithm to avoid local minima and increasing the diversity of the trained individuals. Five structural mutations are applied sequentially to each network: node deletion, connection deletion, node addition, connection addition and node fusion. More details about the EA can be found in Martínez-Estudillo et al. (2005, 2006).

397 in this paper. In this figure it is possible to see how the proposed methodology
 398 underestimates H_s for high waves, over 6m. The reason of this bias is that
 399 the proposed methodology looks for a reconstruction of H_s in which the
 400 global error in the series is minimized, but this may lead to local biases
 401 (underestimations in this case) for high waves.

402 The models obtained by the proposed PUNN can be linearized by means
 403 of applying a natural logarithm to the input variables, this way, the obtained
 404 models are directly interpretable. For example, the model obtained to recon-
 405 struct the time series of wave height of buoy 46061 from time series of other
 406 buoys is given by the expression:

$$\ln(\hat{H}_{61}(t) + 0.127) = \ln 0.850 + 0.73 \cdot \ln H_{76}(t) + 0.19 \cdot \ln H_{82}(t) \quad (6)$$

407 Note that this linear expression of the PUNN result involves $\ln(x)$ terms,
 408 and produces a reconstruction of the H_s missing values ($r^2 = 0.88$), with
 409 good performance on information recovery at a global level of the H_s signal,
 410 though with worse results in extreme values. Compare this result with that
 411 of the sigmoid case ($r^2 = 0.87$):

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}_{61}(t) = & 0.9614 + 1.9964 \cdot (1/(1 + e^{-(+2.2277 \cdot (H_{76}(t)) + 0.4217 \cdot (H_{82}(t)) - 1.0683)})) \\ 412 & - 0.6161 \cdot (1/(1 + e^{-(0.0248 \cdot (H_{82}(t)) + 2.4038)})), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

413 The complete recovering of series using the proposed PUNN for all the
 414 buoys considered are shown in Figure 5, and a comparative between recon-
 415 structed test data and real test data is shown in Figure 6. Note that the
 416 proposed method allows a complete reconstruction of all the buoys with a
 417 reasonable accuracy, in spite of the massive missing data of the initial time
 418 series.

419 We can discuss that the Table 5 shows:

- 420 • The wave height of the buoy 46061 (nearby coast) is a linear combina-
 421 tion of wave height of nearby coast buoys, where buoy 46076 has more
 422 importance to estimate it.
- 423 • It occurs, in a similar way, on the estimation of the wave height of buoy
 424 46076.
- 425 • The buoy 46078 only depends on the wave height of the buoy 46001
 426 (both offshore buoys), so the RMSE in this case is larger.

- 427 • The nearby coast buoy 46082 wave height is reconstructed using the
428 wave height of the buoys 46076 and 46061 (nearby coast), and the buoy
429 46085 (offshore), where the most important is the 46076.
- 430 • Finally, the wave height of the offshore buoy 46085 depends on the
431 buoy 46001 and curiously on the buoy 46082 (nearby coast).

432 5. Conclusions

433 The reconstruction of massive missing data in ocean buoys is a hard prob-
434 lem, with important applications in marine structures management, such as
435 oil platforms or energy harvesting devices, to name a few. In general, the
436 problem can be tackled using a complete set of data, common for all buoys
437 considered, from which different reconstruction algorithms can be trained.
438 That approach cannot be applied, however, in the case of massive missing
439 data or a large amount of buoys to be reconstructed, since in this case, the
440 size of the common available data for all buoys is reduced a lot. In this paper
441 we propose the use of a Evolutionary Unit Neural Network (EPUNN) with
442 partial reconstruction using linear models as inputs to solve this problem.
443 Missing data reconstruction in two steps is proposed, in such a way that the
444 linear models are applied to obtain a preliminary complete reconstruction
445 of the buoys, and the EPUNN is applied later, using linear models outputs
446 as network's inputs. In this paper we also show the potential of the pro-
447 posed EPUNN to obtain simple reconstruction models that can be better
448 interpreted than the models out of traditional neural networks. In the ex-
449 perimental section of the paper we have shown the good performance of the
450 proposed approach in a real case of massive missing data reconstruction in 6
451 wave-rider buoys at the Gulf of Alaska, with slightly underestimation of H_s
452 for high waves over 6m. Future studies will face the problem of H_s recovering
453 in location with extreme values, while keeping the reconstruction capability
454 in the rest of the time series. Multi-objective approaches can be applied to
455 this problem, since global and local metrics are, in general, opposed. The
456 wave height data are used as an example in this paper, but note that the
457 proposed method may be similarly applied to other gappy data sets obtained
458 through various ocean observing systems (e.g., Liu et al. (2015)). However,
459 one should be cautious in using such reconstructed data for scientific appli-
460 cations before examining their accuracies.

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Table 1: Summary of characteristics for the considered buoys.

Buoy/Values	Water depth (m)	# Missing values	# Available	# Test
46001	4206	0	8767	-
46061	204	1026	7740	1548
46076	201	3099	5667	1133
46078	3404	5158	3609	722
46082	296	1158	7608	1522
46085	3736	4138	4629	926

Table 2: Correlation coefficients between time series (H_s (m)).

Buoy	46001	46061	46076	46078	46082	46085
46001	1	0.669806	0.747141	0.817531	0.719842	0.817857
46061	0.669806	1	0.898728	0.615648	0.855197	0.697182
46076	0.747141	0.898728	1	0.678350	0.871085	0.742769
46078	0.817531	0.615648	0.678350	1	0.620373	0.664483
46082	0.719842	0.855197	0.871085	0.620373	1	0.795784
46085	0.817857	0.697182	0.742769	0.664483	0.795784	1

Table 3: Results of transfer functions LM.

Buoy	Model	RMSE test [meters]	r^2
Iteration 1			
46076	$\hat{H}_{76}(t) = 0.2479 + 0.6687H_{01}(t - 1)$	0.7258	0.8236
46078	$\hat{H}_{78}(t) = 0.5234 + 0.8172H_{01}(t)$	0.8657	0.7474
46085	$\hat{H}_{85}(t) = 0.4020 + 0.8859H_{01}(t)$	0.8590	0.8354
Iteration 2			
46061	$\hat{H}_{61}(t) = 0.1589 + 0.6588H_{76}(t)$	0.5840	0.8389
46082	$\hat{H}_{82}(t) = 0.2791 + 0.9806H_{76}(t)$	0.8308	0.8339

Table 4: Results of the neighbors LM.

Buoy	RMSE test [meters]	r^2
46061	0.7086	0.7507
46076	0.7178	0.8335
46078	1.0946	0.6313
46082	0.9324	0.7851
46085	0.8898	0.8276

Table 5: Results of the proposed PUNN.

Buoy	Model	RMSE [meters]	r^2
46061	$\hat{H}_{61}(t) = -0.127 + 0.850 \cdot H_{76}(t)^{0.73} \cdot H_{82}(t)^{0.19}$ $\ln(\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{61}(\mathbf{t}) + \mathbf{0.127}) = \ln \mathbf{0.850} + \mathbf{0.73} \cdot \ln \mathbf{H}_{76}(\mathbf{t}) + \mathbf{0.19} \cdot \ln \mathbf{H}_{82}(\mathbf{t})$	0.5045	0.8785
46076	$\hat{H}_{76}(t) = -0.056 + 1.238 \cdot H_{61}(t)^{0.60} \cdot H_{82}(t)^{0.35}$ $\ln(\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{76}(\mathbf{t}) + \mathbf{0.056}) = \ln \mathbf{1.238} + \mathbf{0.60} \cdot \ln \mathbf{H}_{61}(\mathbf{t}) + \mathbf{0.35} \cdot \ln \mathbf{H}_{82}(\mathbf{t})$	0.4435	0.9353
46078	$\hat{H}_{78}(t) = -0.685 + 1.829 \cdot H_{01}(t)^{0.66}$ $\ln(\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{78}(\mathbf{t}) + \mathbf{0.685}) = \ln \mathbf{1.829} + \mathbf{0.66} \cdot \ln \mathbf{H}_{01}(\mathbf{t})$	0.8571	0.7518
46082	$\hat{H}_{82}(t) = 0.105 + 1.099 \cdot H_{61}(t)^{0.30} \cdot H_{76}(t)^{0.51} \cdot H_{85}(t-1)^{0.22}$ $\ln(\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{82}(\mathbf{t}) - \mathbf{0.105}) = \ln \mathbf{1.099} + \mathbf{0.30} \cdot \ln \mathbf{H}_{61}(\mathbf{t}) + \mathbf{0.51} \cdot \ln \mathbf{H}_{76}(\mathbf{t}) + \mathbf{0.22} \cdot \ln \mathbf{H}_{85}(\mathbf{t} - \mathbf{1})$	0.6183	0.9110
46085	$\hat{H}_{85}(t) = -0.087 + 1.303 \cdot H_{01}(t)^{0.50} \cdot H_{82}(t+1)^{0.38}$ $\ln(\hat{\mathbf{H}}_{85}(\mathbf{t}) + \mathbf{0.087}) = \ln \mathbf{1.303} + \mathbf{0.50} \cdot \ln \mathbf{H}_{01}(\mathbf{t}) + \mathbf{0.38} \cdot \ln \mathbf{H}_{82}(\mathbf{t} + \mathbf{1})$	0.6972	0.8961

Table 6: Results of neural networks with sigmoid units.

Buoy	Model	RMSE [meters]	r^2
46061	$\hat{H}_{61}(t) = 0.9614 + 1.9964 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{-(2.2277 \cdot (H_{76}(t)) + 0.4217 \cdot (H_{82}(t)) - 1.0683)}} \right) - 0.6161 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{-(0.0248 \cdot (H_{82}(t)) + 2.4038)}} \right)$	0.5104	0.8749
46076	$\hat{H}_{76}(t) = -0.6050 + 3.1945 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{-(+1.0527 \cdot (H_{61}(t)) + 0.4821 \cdot (H_{82}(t)) + 0.0153)}} \right) - 4.7115 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{-(0.3315 \cdot (H_{61}(t)) - 3.6091)}} \right)$	0.4400	0.9363
46078	$\hat{H}_{78}(t) = 1.8085 - 3.1525 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{-(2.5757 \cdot (H_{01}(t)) - 0.9281)}} \right) + 0.0706 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{-(3.9206 \cdot (H_{01}(t)) - 4.8965)}} \right)$	0.8546	0.7532
46082	$\hat{H}_{82}(t) = -0.3886 + 2.5658 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{-(+0.7866 \cdot (H_{61}(t)) + 1.022 \cdot (H_{76}(t)) + 0.4834 \cdot (H_{85}(t-1)) - 0.0808)}} \right) + 0.1002 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{-(2.5054 \cdot (H_{61}(t)) + 0.7903 \cdot (H_{76}(t)) - 4.3730 \cdot (H_{85}(t-1)) - 2.2912)}} \right)$	0.6074	0.9139
46085	$\hat{H}_{85}(t) = -1.4756 + 4.8223 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{-(+0.4622 \cdot (H_{01}(t)) + 0.4281 \cdot (H_{82}(t+1)) - 0.01756)}} \right) - 0.4596 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{-(+1.0096 \cdot (H_{01}(t)) - 3.4734)}} \right)$	0.7026	0.8950

Figure 1: Outline of the proposed methodology.

Figure 2: Selected buoys at Gulf of Alaska.

(a) Iteration 1

(b) Iteration 2

Figure 3: Transfer functions LM procedure.

(a) 46061

(b) 46076

(c) 46078

(d) 46082

(e) 46085

Figure 4: Scatter plots (PUNN model, test set) for the different buoys considered.

Figure 5: Reconstructed time series H_s (m) with the proposed PUNN. Red lines delimit test areas used in our experiments. The reconstruction of these areas can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Reconstructed test data $H_s(m)$ vs real test data. Blue lines are the reconstruction over the testing area represented by green lines.